

Enabling Novel Smart Grid Energy Services with the Nobel Grid Architecture

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Abstract—Changes in electricity markets, driven by the increased use of renewable energy resources and the active participation of consumers in managing their energy usage, creates a demand for new smart grid technologies and services. In this paper, we describe an architecture that has been developed within the EU-funded Nobel Grid project, integrating novel smart grid solutions and services to enable energy flexibility markets, with enhanced demand-response schemes and active prosumer participation. The architecture was developed using the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM) Framework from CEN-CENELEC-ETSI. In this way, the business context and use cases have been modelled, along with the necessary components, communication protocols and data models that are necessary to realise the Nobel Grid project’s ambitious goals of a more open energy market.

Index Terms—Smart Grid Security Architecture, Smart Grid Architecture Model, SGAM

I. INTRODUCTION

The electricity market is undergoing major changes, primarily because of a greater use of renewable energy resources and a drive towards energy efficiency. New energy market roles are being introduced, alongside the established energy producers, Transmission and Distribution System Operators (TSOs and DSOs), and energy retailers. A key new actor is the *prosumer* that both consumes and produces energy. Prosumers can offer flexibility for active demand-response services by shifting, increasing or decreasing power consumption and production. Consequently, flexibility becomes a commodity in the market and is handled by *aggregators* and *Balance Responsible Parties (BRP)*. In addition, *Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)* offer auxiliary services, mainly oriented around notification and monitoring of energy production, storage and consumption. Alongside these market developments, and in order to support them, the electricity grid is being transformed into a *smart grid* through an increased use of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) for monitoring and control purposes.

These changes form the background to the EU-funded Nobel Grid project, whose objective is to address the needs of these new market roles. Nobel Grid aims to improve many aspects of energy distribution and retail market, from renewable energy source integration, energy information shar-

ing among stakeholders to enhancement of the distribution grid management. To support these ambitious goals, we have developed the Nobel Grid architecture. In order to manage the scale and complexity of the Nobel Grid architecture, four major sub-systems have been defined: (i) a Demand Responsive Flexible Market (DRFM) Cockpit for aggregators, ESCOs and retailers; (ii) an Energy Management and Analytics (EMA) App to support engagement with industrial and domestic prosumers; (iii) the Unbundled Smart Meter (USM) for prosumers, providing both metrology functionality and a platform for energy services; and (iv) the Grid Monitor and Control Master (G3M) Framework, providing advanced grid management functions for DSOs.

The Nobel Grid architecture has been specified using the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM) Framework [1] from CEN-CENELEC-ETSI. In this paper, we present a complete architecture model including the business context associated with the Nobel Grid project, the use cases that support the project’s business goals, and the ICT architecture that underpins the implementation of the Nobel Grid use cases.

II. RELATED WORK

An important challenge, especially in the European electricity market, is the efficient integration of distributed renewable energy sources. To support this integration, efforts have been made towards real-time market models for renewables operation [2], and energy storage for grid balancing (e.g. [3]), as well as different methods for management and control of distributed resources, e.g., the heterarchical approach [4]. Renewable energy sources enable flexible markets and demand-response, which require active consumer and prosumer participation in the energy management process. In [5], a comprehensive technical and commercial architecture to enable active demand-response has been developed. Moreover, demand response and enhanced grid monitoring has been used for improvement of the low-voltage energy management grid sector, e.g. [6]. The Nobel Grid project builds on this work and goes one step further, targeting a more holistic and integrated approach, including the development of novel flexibility schemes that interface with grid management functionality,

both of which are supported by smart metering solution and technology to interact with prosumers.

III. NOBEL GRID ARCHITECTURE

Due to the highly-integrated approach adopted by the Nobel Grid project, it is crucial to find an appropriate method for describing the architecture of the whole system. Arguably, in Europe, the SGAM Framework [1] is the state of the art means of modelling smart grid use cases and architectures. The SGAM Framework is a three dimensional model of the smart grid, specifying the system across five interoperability layers, divided further into domains and zones. Consequently, we used it to describe the Nobel Grid architecture, with support from the SGAM Toolbox [7]. In what follows, we summarise the major aspects of the Nobel Grid architecture for each of the five SGAM interoperability layers: *business, function, component, communication, and information.*

A. The Nobel Grid SGAM Business Layer

At the SGAM business layer, the overall business context is described, including the different stakeholders and their goals. These aspects are defined using three entities: (i) *business actors*; (ii) *business goals*; and (iii) *business use cases*.

There are four main business actors in the Nobel Grid approach: (i) the Aggregator; (ii) the Prosumer; (iii) the Retailer (Supplier); and (iv) the Distribution System Operator (DSO). There are two further important actors: Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) and Third Parties. These are not directly related to the functions that are realised by the Nobel Grid architecture, and act as external entities that provide additional services. These actor definitions are compliant with the energy market roles that are defined in the Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) [8]. Each of these business actors has a set of business goals that are realised through business use cases. For example, the Prosumer actor has the goal of optimising energy usage, and has a corresponding business use case associated with it.

In Nobel Grid, we have defined three main business use cases: (i) *Provide Flexibility Services*; (ii) *Maximise Power Reliability*; and (iii) *Detect and Quickly Resolve Blackouts*. The *Provide Flexibility Services* use case is owned by the Aggregator actor and is used by the Prosumer, if they decide to participate in demand-response programmes. Moreover, it is used by the DSO for grid balancing and by the Retailer for flexibility trading. In general, the purpose of this business use case is to improve energy usage via more active prosumer participation, encouraging them to optimise their energy usage. Consequently, there should be a reduction in carbon emissions and a maximal use of green energy. The two remaining business use cases are defined for the DSO, realising services that are related to grid management and maintenance, optimising system operation for secure and reliable power supply, and to provide system resilience and recovery from blackouts.

B. The Nobel Grid SGAM Function Layer

The SGAM function layer defines hierarchically organized smart grid use cases. High Level Use Cases (HLUCs) reside

at the boundary between the business and function layer, and are directly invoked by business use cases. In what follows, we briefly introduce the HLUCs that are associated with the three Nobel Grid business use cases.

1) *Provide Flexibility Services*: To realise this business use case, five HLUCs are invoked:

Green Energy Max which maximise the usage of *renewables* by provisioning of energy information and device automation;

Prosumer Max which supports prosumers to maximise the usage of the *power* they are generating, ensuring they get the best value for their investment in renewable technologies;

Social Housing enables grid balancing through large-scale electric installations, including the automation of electric heating systems, which is beneficial for aggregators and ESCOs;

The Cooperative Power Plant which introduces the concept of a cooperative Virtual Power Plant (VPP), by combining a large number of small prosumers and a portfolio of larger DER production and balancing capacity; and

Imbalance Reduction that aims to shift consumption to times when reverse power flows occur in substations, by informing customers, which participate in demand-response schemes, about an excess of green energy.

2) *Maximise Power Reliability*: This business use case invokes the following HLUCs:

Controlling the Grid for power quality and security, providing tools to perform continuous and online power quality monitoring, thus reducing the response times to failures;

Increase of Power Quality implements services such as congestion and overvoltage management, analysis and identification of undesirable situations (e.g. reverse power flows, operational limit violations etc.);

Maintaining Grid Assets performs monitoring and maintenance of the MV/LV grid assets, providing a prognosis tool for forecasting potential problems and preventing incidents; and

Power Losses Reduction by power factor management, providing – in real-time – a power factor set point to the producers, engaging prosumers to vary their production according to the grid status.

3) *Detect and Quickly Resolve Blackouts*: Finally, this business use case is realised with two HLUCs:

Efficient Recovery from Power Outages that uses demand flexibility to support grid restoration after a fault, providing services to reconfigure the network topology, in order to isolate a fault and maintain the maximum number of consumers under normal supply; and

Blackout and Incident Management that is used to monitor incidents and manage them in a time-responsive way, in order to avoid bigger (cascading) problems.

These HLUCs are realised by a set of Primary and Secondary Use Cases (PUCs and SUCs) that represent functions and services that are provided by the system. For example,

to realise the HLUC *Prosumer Max*, a PUC called *Retailer using Demand Response for Matching Production and Consumption* has been defined, which makes use of a SUC, called *Aggregator Providing for Automated Demand Response (ADR) Services*. In total, the Nobel Grid architecture model consists of approximately fifty use cases.

In addition to business actors, we defined corresponding *logical actors* at the function layer. These are roles that parts of the system play in the context of a use case. In this way, there is a clear traceability of roles across the system. For example, the *Flexibility Engine* logical actor, which supports the implementation of *Flexibility Services*, realises the role of the Aggregator business actor. Correspondingly, there is a relationship between logical actors and the systems that are defined at the component layer.

C. The Nobel Grid SGAM Component Layer

In the Nobel Grid architecture, components are organized around four major sub-systems. The first one, *Demand Response Flexible Market (DRFM)*, implements the flexibility use cases for aggregators, ESCOs and retailers. The second sub-system - *Energy Management and Analytics (EMA) App* provides an interface for industrial and domestic prosumers, to support their participation in flexibility services. The *Unbundled Smart Meter (USM)* consists of two main parts: a Smart Metrology Meter (SMM) and Smart Meter eXtension (SMX), implementing the role of a smart meter with both metrology and business logic functions, respectively. Additionally, it serves as a gateway to the flexibility within the home environment. Finally, the *Grid Monitor and Control Master (G3M) Framework* realises the use cases for the DSO, including services for command and control, network monitoring and management (configuration), and data analytics. Figure 1 depicts the overall distribution of the Nobel Grid components across the SGAM domains and zones. To realise the Nobel Grid use cases, there are interactions between sub-systems, primarily between the USM and the G3M Framework – to support grid control and maintenance – the DRFM Cockpit and EMA App – to support prosumer engagement – and between the G3M Framework and DRFM Cockpit sub-systems – to support interactions between flexibility services and grid management functions. To enable these interactions, a set of common components have been specified. Different instances of these will be installed and configured for the corresponding sub-systems. Three common components have been defined:

Data Acquisition and Control Frontend (DACF) enables interaction between the USM and all the other sub-systems. This will be a repository of drivers and services that can be used to realise communication with the USM, covering all the protocols that are required (see Sec. III-D). This module could also be configured to periodically and asynchronously received data from smart grid elements.

Actor Specific Data Repository (ASDR) plays the role of a real-time database and a middleware interoperability service. Aligned with the EU policies for data holding

and retention [9], the ASDR will enable different policies for data access.

Actor Specific Big Data Repository (ASBDR) stores the historical measures that are related to the smart grid, and is used for the purposes that are specific for each sub-system.

We briefly introduce details of each of the major Nobel Grid sub-systems, highlighting how they interact via these common components.

a) *The USM Components*: At the intersection of the SGAM Customer Premises zone and Field domain, the components related to the USM and Smart Home Environment are located. These include the *SMX Core*, which executes real-time applications, and the *SMX Real-Time Database*. The SMX architecture is database-centric. Consequently, applications exchange smart metering data through the real-time database, to which access is controlled via a Role Based Access Control (RBAC) system, configured according to the country-specific and customer-defined policies. *Smart Home Services* support the control of *Smart Home Intelligent Controllers (SHIC)*, which provides an interface and means of communication to the home environment, including loads.

b) *G3M Framework Components*: At the core of the G3M Framework is the *G3M Web Server*. This component is a client of both the real-time ASDR and the historical ASBDR. In addition, the *G3M Web Server* provides a web-based user interface, called the *G3M GUI*. The displayed content and functionality that is available via this interface will be dependent on the profile and role of the user. In addition, the mobile G3M GUI will be available for the DSO field workers. The *G3M Event Dispatcher* is responsible for controlling the schedule of various working tasks. The monitoring of the smart grid state, measures and events is realised by the *G3M Data Analysis* component, whereas the *Prognosis Service* offers different electrical calculation functionality (e.g. steady state calculator). The optimization of grid behaviour, based on prognosis information, is performed by the *Grid Manager*. Finally, the *VPP Manager* component is used for VPP management, including collecting measurements from DERs and offering aggregated services.

c) *DRFM Cockpit Components*: In the core of the DRFM Cockpit is the *DRFM Web Server*. It performs core services, such as creating demand-response strategies, billing and optimal tariff schemas, portfolio analytics, fault diagnostics, and maintenance services. These services can be accessed through the *DRFM Graphical User Interface*, and via interfaces that are provided by other Nobel Grid components, using *DRFM Nobel Grid Data Repository*. The *Flexibility Engine* component calculates consumers' demand flexibility and profiles. An ASDR component provides real-time analytics about consumers, and acts as a middleware that captures data from USMs, disseminating it to the *DRFM Web Server* and *Flexibility Engine*. Along with the real-time status of consumer portfolios, access to historical data is provided by the *DRFM Big Data Repository*, whose role is to act as the central repository for aggregators, ESCOs, and retailers.

Fig. 1. The Nobel Grid SGAM Component Layer

d) *EMA App Components*: There are three components associated with the EMA App sub-system: a central control server, a local client on the USM, and a user interface. The *EMA App Central Control Server* is the back-end of the EMA App system, and performs data analysis that combines information from different data sources, e.g., the DRFM Cockpit, served by ASDR and ASBDR instances. Additionally, it enables communication with other Nobel Grid components and third-parties (the latter through an open API). The *EMA App SMX Client* component is located on the *SMX Core*. It collects local data, e.g., related to the smart home environment, and delivers it to the ASDR and subsequently the *EMA App Central Control Server*. The *EMA App User Interface* is the primary means of interaction with the prosumer, and is available as a smartphone application and a web-based interface.

D. The Nobel Grid SGAM Communication Layer

The communication protocols that are used between the different Nobel Grid components have been drawn from those recommended by the CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Smart Grid

Coordination Group (SG-CG) [10]. In summary, the main communication protocols are:

DLMS/COSEM [11] used for the Advanced Meter Reading (AMR) and other data exchange, including billing data from tariff data, load profiles, instrumentation values read with DLMS/COSEM, power quality data (PQ) and events.

IEC 61850 [12] for Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) and other smart grid related activities, including DER monitoring and control.

OpenADR [13] used to support demand-response activities – specifically, we make use of the V2.0b Profile Specification, which in 2015 also became IEC/PAS 62746-10-1 [13] for Demand Response.

MQTT or other M2M protocols [14] MQTT is a lightweight, in terms of footprint and network requirements, publish-subscribe protocol that can be used on top of the TCP/IP protocol suite. MQTT is used, along with other M2M communication protocols, to support the implementation of energy services.

E. The Nobel Grid SGAM Information Layer

The information layer of the SGAM Framework is mostly focused on the information objects and the specification of data model standards used for their exchange. For the data models that will be used internally by the different sub-systems or used to exchange data, the Nobel Grid project has adopted the following standards:

The Common Information Model (CIM) [15] is primarily being used in the G3M Framework. In addition, the abstract representation of CIM will be used in the DRFM Cockpit – it will be extended to support flexibility concepts to support aggregation.

DLMS/COSEM [11] the Companion Specification for Energy Metering (COSEM) data model will be used for the messages exchanged between the DACF and the USM for AMR. Data will be encapsulated in Device Language Message Specification (DLMS) frames.

IEC 61850 [12] data model standard will be used for the SCADA-related functions and communication with grid elements and DERs.

OpenADR [13] provides a simple data model that will be used by the DRFM Cockpit and SMX for demand-response activities.

In a number of cases, harmonisation between the different data models will be required, in order to realise the overall Nobel Grid vision. To achieve this harmonisation, we will build on ongoing standards activities: the IEC 62361-102 standard will provide rules for interfacing the CIM data model with IEC 61850; IEC 62056-6-9 defines a mapping between the CIM (IEC 61968-9) and DLMS/COSEM (IEC 62056) data models and message profiles; and IEC 61850-80-4 provides a mapping of the COSEM metering model over IEC 61850. Figure 2 summarises these intersection points in the overall Nobel Grid architecture.

Fig. 2. The three main data models that will be applied in the Nobel Grid project, and the points where harmonisation will be required.

IV. SECURITY AND PRIVACY ASPECTS

Security and privacy are major concerns in the smart grid – cyber-attacks could result in operational consequences, as seen in the Ukraine in 2015 [16], and high resolution smart meter measurements could be used for intrusive behavioural

profiling, for example. To address security aspects, we have followed a process advocated by Uslar *et al.* [17] to identify security requirements, wherein the Nobel Grid logical actors are mapped to the those specified in the NISTIR 7628 smart grid security guidelines [18]. In these guidelines, groups of interfaces between actors are assigned high-level security requirements. The main requirements, that have been identified for the Nobel Grid architecture are summarized below:

Access Control should be implemented for all interfaces accessible via Internet, especially, the authentication and encryption are required for remote access. The access to the system should be terminated after a defined inactivity period (addressing requirements such as session lock, concurrent session handling and remote session termination).

Audit and Accountability emphasises importance of the non-repudiation, that could be implemented by digital signature or logging, for example.

Identification and Authentication requirements focus on mechanisms that enable unique identification of both, users and devices. Moreover, the feedback of authentication during the process should be obscured.

Information System and Communication Protection require security measures to prevent disclosure or illegitimate use (or reuse) of information at rest and on the fly. Encryption should be provided for information considered critical or privacy sensitive. In addition, effects of denial-of-service attacks should be mitigated by filtering certain types of packets within internal network, for example.

Application Partitioning is required for clear separation of user functionality (interface) and core smart grid system management functions.

Boundary Protection requirement assumes that grid subsystems are defined, and communication between internal and external zones are monitored and protected.

Smart Grid Information System and Information Integrity recommends use of integrity verification tools that look for evidence of information tampering, errors or omissions.

There are potential privacy risks associated with the Nobel Grid use cases, in particular, with those associated with the *Flexibility Services* business use case. To assess these risks and identify appropriate privacy controls, we have followed a data protection risk assessment (DPIA). Results of the study will be considered in future Nobel Grid system developments, especially focusing on communication of the SMX (Prosumer) with DRFM (Aggregator) and EMA App (ESCo).

V. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, we have presented the Nobel Grid architecture, which we have modelled using the SGAM Framework, which has provided us with a structured approach to architecture modelling, and supported alignment with smart grid standardization efforts from CEN-CENELEC-ETSI. A major benefit of the SGAM Framework is *traceability* across the different

interoperability layers, enabling the choice of system elements to be rationalised in a top-down and bottom-up manner.

Furthermore, the SGAM Framework handles complexity of the smart grid system using interoperability layers, in which domain-specific content is described at a given layer in a form that is approachable to experts from other disciplines. We found this aspect particularly useful in the Nobel Grid project, as it supported the development of a common understanding across partners from multiple disciplines.

Moving forward, the project will continue to develop the sub-systems that are described in the Nobel Grid architecture. A consequence of this will be a more detailed specification of the data models that are used for component interaction. The developed solutions will be evaluated in five demonstration sites, located across Europe.

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